

OCEAN ICE News – May 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to May's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community. Happy Easter!

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including the upcoming webinars hosted by the European Polar Board, highlighting April's Climate Coffee and participation on an Ocean Research Cruise. We have upcoming Climate Coffees that you can register for in May, June and September. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in June!

Congratulations! University of Delaware is now an official associated partner in OCEAN ICE

We congratulate University of Delaware on becoming an official associated partner!

We welcome Carlos Moffat from University of Delaware. His role in OCEAN ICE will be mostly within WP1 and WP2. His work will be contributing to efforts to understand the processes modulating the ocean circulation and properties along the Antarctic continental shelf, which in turn impact continental ice retreat, sea ice dynamics, and marine ecosystems.

Researcher in the Spotlight: David Chandler

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on David Chandler, a Senior Researcher at [NORCE](#).

Read the feature on David [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Webinar Series

The OCEAN ICE webinar series, hosted by the European Polar Board, is set to continue! The webinars offer insights into the OCEAN ICE project, showcasing ongoing research, key findings, and expected outcomes from various work packages.

On the 8th of April, EPB presented a webinar for WP7 on Data Management, here's a summary on what the webinar covered:

This is the third webinar in the series introducing the OCEAN ICE project. In this session, we explore data management within the project (Work Package 7 / WP7), with a special focus on using Jupyter Notebooks and Google Colab for polar research. Our invited speakers, Mariaclaudia Paolini (Project Manager, ETT) and Pietro Viglino (Backend Developer, ETT), present an overview of the OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan and infrastructure design, followed by a hands-on demonstration showing how these tools can be used to work with and elaborate research data. The webinar concludes with a public Q&A session. This series is hosted by the European Polar Board and moderated by Eva Horovcakova, EPB Senior Communications Officer. More about WP7: <https://ocean-ice.eu/about/project-st...>

Catch up on the webinar here: [OCEAN ICE WP7 Webinar - Data Management](#)

Don't miss out - join the conversation and stay informed about the latest developments of the project.

Read the description of the upcoming webinars **Upcoming events!**

OCEAN:ICE EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD

OCEAN ICE WP7 WEBINAR

DATA MANAGEMENT

This webinar will be the third in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

8 April 2025
14:00 CEST

@ Dr. Fenulka Ederhe

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe Funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – April

Catch up on April's Climate Coffee with David Chandler on Warming of circumpolar deep water: a million-year perspective on recent changes around Antarctica [here](#).

Future climate and sea level projections depend sensitively on Antarctic Ice Sheet response to ocean-driven melting and the resulting freshwater fluxes into the Southern Ocean. Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) in the Southern Ocean is increasingly recognised as a crucial heat source for ice shelf melt. Quantifying past changes in the temperature of CDW is therefore of great benefit for modelling ice sheet response to past warm climates, and for putting recent and projected CDW temperature changes into context. Here we use marine sedimentary evidence to estimate CDW temperature changes over the last eight glacial-interglacial cycles (800,000 years). Estimated interglacial warming reached 0.6 ± 0.4 °C relative to present, while glacial cooling was typically -1.5 to -2 °C. The peak warmth occurred in the last interglacial, when sea-levels were a few metres higher than present. For comparison, observations indicate CDW warming of around 0.1 °C/decade since the 1990s, while climate projections (CMIP6 SP585) suggest 0.6 °C warming could already be reached by 2100.

16 April 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Dave Chandler (NORCE)

Warming of circumpolar deep water: a million-year perspective on recent changes around Antarctica

OCEAN ICE: Ocean Research Cruise

Jing Jin from OCEAN ICE volunteered on a research cruise led by Professor Jonathan Sharples at the University of Liverpool. The project, Enhanced carbon export driven by internal tides over the mid-Atlantic ridge (CarTRidge), is to test the effects of internal tidal waves on the phytoplankton, which is an important part of the oceanic biological carbon pump, over the mid-Atlantic ridge.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE - Role of the Poles Cross-Cutting Theme Meeting

The spring 2025 meeting of the Role of the Poles cross-cutting theme was held on 8th May. There was a presentation by Dave Chandler from NORCE about ongoing work with NorESM2 in WP5, featuring their evaluation the model's simulation of water masses along selected S-N sections in the Southern Ocean and global climate simulations with imposed Antarctic freshwater fluxes following the SOFIA protocol and using the Fast Track FWF product from WP4. There was an interesting discussion of how to take into account fluxes already simulated in climate models to avoid double counting the input in these simulations. We also heard updates on other progress in WPs 4, 5 and 6, including work quantifying the shelf melt / ocean stratification feedback loop occurring at PIK, and the derivation of new understanding of the force balance on different sizes of icebergs being developed at BAS

OCEAN ICE Deliverables and Milestones submitted

The OCEAN ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables and milestones:

- D4.1 [‘Fast-track’ sensitivity of freshwater fluxes to climate scenarios](#)
- D5.7 [‘Initialisation and verification of NEMO configuration’](#)
- D5.8 [‘Greenland ice sheet freshwater implementation in NorESM’](#)
- D1.3 [‘Comparison and validation of two Antarctic SSH products’](#)
- MS10 [‘Recovery of moorings in South Sandwich Trench’](#)

The progress and results of OCEAN ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have three upcoming Climate Coffee events, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Inga Sauer on Extreme weather events: tipping points & societal implications
22 May 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

22 May 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online
Inga Sauer (PIK)

Extreme weather events: tipping points and societal implications

The poverty implications of increasing frequencies of extreme weather events - identifying tipping points across households from different income groups

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Pietro Viglino on Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, drawing on the experience in the OCEAN ICE project
12 June 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

12 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online
Pietro Viglino (ETT)

Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, drawing on the experience in the OCEAN ICE project

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Audrey Minière on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

25 September 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

Estimating ocean warming: challenges
and recommendations for robust
assessment

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE WP4 Webinar: Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing

Join us for the next webinar in the OCEAN ICE series, this time spotlighting Work Package 4 (WP4) dedicated to Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing.

This webinar will feature talks by: Jan De Rydt, Northumbria University (Introduction to Work Package 4) Frank Pattyn, Université Libre de Bruxelles (Deep Uncertainty in Freshwater Fluxes) Vio Coulon, Université Libre de Bruxelles (Future Freshwater Fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet) Qing Qin, Northumbria University (Calibration of Ice-Sheet Melt Parameterizations)

Date and time: 13th May, 10:30 CEST

Registration Here: [Webinar Registration - Zoom](#)

OCEAN ICE webinar series is facilitated by the [European Polar Board](#).

OCEAN:ICE **EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD**

OCEAN ICE WP4 WEBINAR

QUANTIFICATION OF ANTARCTIC ICE SHEET DEEP UNCERTAINTY AND FRESHWATER FLUXES UNDER CLIMATE FORCING

This webinar will be the fourth in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

13 May 2025
10:30 CEST

© Dr Renuka Badhe

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE WP1/10 Webinar: Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export

Join us for the next webinar in the OCEAN ICE series, this time spotlighting Work Package 1 (WP1) & Work Package 10 dedicated to Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export.

WP1 addresses the key processes, connectivity and circulation of the Antarctic shelf seas. An ambitious circumpolar programme of instrument deployments, including mooring and novel profiling float arrays over the continental shelf is proposed.

WP10 focuses on implementing the oceanographic component of WISH-OI and linking results to WP1. It will ensure that the NASC scientists can benefit from training measures and knowledge exchange activities to operate instrumentation, perform post-processing of data in order to perform the work of analysis of the on the thermohaline structure of regional water masses, transformation of shelf water, formation of the frontal zone in the Bransfield Strait.

Date and time: 22nd May, 14:00 CEST

Registration Here: [Webinar Registration - Zoom](#)

OCEAN ICE webinar series is facilitated by the [European Polar Board](#).

OCEAN ICE WP2 Webinar: Cryosphere-ocean interaction, processes and feedbacks

Don't miss the next webinar in the OCEAN ICE series, where we'll turn our focus to Work Package 2 (WP2), exploring Cryosphere-ocean interaction, processes and feedbacks About WP2: WP2 focuses on the key role that ice sheet-ocean interaction plays in melting ice shelves and the export and freshwater distribution of icebergs. Innovative AUV deployments under 'warm' ice shelves and the first such observations targeted at grounded icebergs will be conducted (supported by South Korean partners), along with observations of 'cold' ice shelf cavity circulation, isotopic concentrations and mixing via a Norwegian-supported borehole. These observations will push forward the state-of-the-art in model basal melt tuning and the development of new parameterisations of iceberg dynamics and oxygen isotope tracking for key community models (NEMO, UKESM). These in turn will inform WP4-6 modelling, examining future ice sheet dynamics and climate coupling.

Date and time: 23rd May, 14:00 CEST

Registration Here: [Webinar Registration - Zoom](#)

OCEAN ICE webinar series is facilitated by the [European Polar Board](#).

OCEAN ICE at UNOC3 European Digital Ocean Pavilion

OCEAN ICE has been accepted to be presented during the EU Digital Ocean Pavilion in Nice (9-13 June) and will be showcased in the exhibition.

Read more [here](#).

A 10-minute keynote talk on “the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on sea level rise – the OCEAN ICE project” has also been accepted and Andrew Meijers will deliver a presentation during the Rising Sea Levels session (10:30 till 13:30 on 11 June 2025) in the INSPIRE area.

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 16 May, 11:00 CEST, Isotope Cross Cutting Theme Meeting, Online
- 19 May 2025, Antarctica InSync Science Webinar, online
- 22 May 2025, Antarctica InSync Science Webinar, online
- 3rd June, Policy event | EBCD & EPB/EU Polar Cluster update, Brussels, Belgium
- 2-13 June 2025, [United Nations Ocean Conference \(UNOC3\)](#), Nice
- 20-25 July 2025, [Busan IAMAS-IACS-IAPSO Joint Assembly 2025 \(JMCP20\)](#), the Republic of Korea

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

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